

Preparing for the quest of lunar fairy castles: high resolution 3D surface mapping S.G. Els^{1,2}, S.K. Amilineni², S. Le Mouélic³, Z. Ioannou⁴, N. Theret⁵, C. Woehler⁶, ¹ Centre for Research and Engineering in Space Technologies (CREST), Université Libre de Brussels, Belgium (sebastian.georg.els@ulb.be), ²Mohammed Bin Rashid Space Centre, Dubai, United Arab Emirates, ³Laboratoire de Planétologie et Géosciences, CNRS UMR 6112, Nantes Université, France, ⁴Physics Department, College of Science, Sultan Qaboos University, Muscat, Oman, ⁵Centre National d'Etudes Spatiales, Toulouse, France, ⁶Image Analysis Group, Technische Universität Dortmund, Otto-Hahn-Strasse 4, 44227 Dortmund, Germany

Introduction: The lunar surface structure at scales below approximately 10 cm has been studied in-situ in a very limited manner only. The sub-millimeter structure has been inferred mainly by means of its optical properties, which are commonly explained by the Hapke model [1] which suggests a surface layer of highly irregular and porous vertical structures at the scale of 10s-100s of microns. These structures are thought to be built in large part by the settling of electrostatically levitated grains. Recent photometric observations by LRO of fresh crater ejecta indicate that the involved processes are giving measurable effects on timescales of 10 years or so [2]. Only few images of the lunar surface at the 100 micron scales have been obtained during the Apollo 11, 12, 14 missions using the ALSCC instrument. These allowed for roughness measurements at the 100 micron level [3].

The lunar rovers Rashid 1 and Rashid 2 of the Emirates Lunar Mission program carry instrumentation aimed to investigate in-situ the undisturbed lunar surface structures at scales smaller than previously observed. The microscopic imager CAM-M [4] in conjunction with a set of Langmuir probes [5] onboard these rovers enable the unprecedented opportunity to observe, and experiment with, the regolith surface grains in their undisturbed environment. While Rashid 1 was destroyed in the crash of the commercial lander which was carrying this rover to the Moon in 2023, its successor, Rashid 2, is expected to be operational on the lunar surface in the close future. This rover is largely a copy of Rashid 1 and carries mostly the same type of scientific instrumentation [6].

Here, we want to illustrate the collection and analysis of the regolith close-up imaging capabilities, and 3D surface imaging potential of the Rashid 2 rover CAM-M system.

The CAM-M instrument: The CAM-M camera is one of the instruments in the science suite of the Rashid 1 and Rashid 2 type rovers. The details of this camera are described in [4]. In brief, it is a 2048x2048 pixel RGB camera mounted at the front side of the rover viewing the lunar surface under an angle of 40°. Its field of view covers approximately 40x50mm² with a spatial sampling varying between 19 to 27 micron/px across the vertical direction of the field of view.

Surface reconstruction: Our approach in this work is to investigate the surface structure using the

optical imaging provided by CAM-M by means of photogrammetry of what we call image strips, i.e., partly overlapping images covering a certain surface area along the rover's drive direction. The ultimate quality of such a reconstruction depends particularly on the image overlap and image quality [7]. Obviously, larger overlaps between images are preferable since they provide a greater number of baselines for stereoscopic analysis. However, considering the rather large file size of the images (uncompressed 5MB), a practical compromise has to be found. As a minimum we consider the image offset of half the vertical field of view, which results in at least two baselines for most points within the images. Corresponding to image separations of ~2cm appears a feasible approach, while still being able to cover a surface stretch of approximately 10-20cm. Here we address the question of what could be achieved using this technique with CAM-M in view of measuring regolith surface roughness, undulations, and features. Again the data were used which were collected using the engineering model rover from Rashid 1 which were described in [4]. The setup in the MBRSC small Moon Yard sand box was used. This contains quartz sand of known particle size distribution. On top of this sand thin layers of LHS-1 and LMS-1 [8] were sprinkled. The surface was not particularly arranged, only that it was roughly falling within the camera's depth of field as it was aimed to collect data of varying focus quality. Finally, several beads were placed/pushed on this surface, mimicking spherules. Then the rover-mounted CAM-M was taking images in an operational sequence of: drive 2cm – take image – drive 2cm – and so on. An extract of the original strip of stitched images, generated using PTGui is shown, in Fig. 1.

To derive the 3 dimensional surface shape, the Agisoft Metashape software was used. In Fig. 2 the resulting Digital Elevation Map (DEM) is shown. It can be seen that this initial vertical reconstruction shows surface structures to a relative of level down to approximately 100 microns, while the horizontal pixel scale is at the 80 micron/px level. The reliability of the absolute reconstruction can be verified against the known size of the bead (Fig. 3).

Outlook and future work: The 3D reconstruction of the surface using such rather sparse data acquisition appears to be able to provide surface structure reconstruction at the 100 micron level and absolute shape measurements at a similar level. The aim

now is to improve this line of analysis further to allow to detect in-situ the long projected fairy castles and other surface features, ultimately to enbalbe the correlation with other surface alteration processes, in particular electrostatic surface charging and dust levitation.

Figure 1 Undistorted, demosaiced, and stitched CAM-M images covering approximately 120mm x 40mm. Visible are also several beads of 8mm diameter tugged into the surface dust layer which here consists of LHS-1 simulant.

References: [1] Hapke, B. (2012) Theory of Reflectance and Emittance Spectroscopy, 2nd ed. [2] Speyerer, E. et al. (2025, June 1). Ephemeral Scars: Electrostatic Dust Redistribution in the Epiregolith Around New Lunar Craters. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15576489>. [3] Helfenstein P. & Shepard M.K. (1999) *Icarus* 141, 107. [4] Els S.G, et al. (2024) *Space Sci. Rev.*, 220, 81. [5] Clausen L., et al. (2025) *Space Sci. Rev.*, 221, 34. [6] AlMatroushi H., et al. (2025, June 1). Rashid 2 Mission: UAE's Second Mission to the Moon Surface. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15470628> [7] AliKaram M.T.M (2025) Coupled Deblurring and 3D Reconstruction from Image Sequences. MSc Thesis Technical University Dortmund [8] Long-Fox J.M., & Britt D.T. (2023) Characterization of planetary regolith simulants for the research and development of space resource technologies. *Front. Space Technol.*4:1255535. doi: 10.3389/frspt.2023.1255535

Figure 2 Digital Elevation Map (DEM) reconstructed from the individual images underlying the image strip shown in Fig.1. The drive direction of the rover was downwards (-y direction).

Figure 3 Cut along the +y direction of the DEM shown in Fig. 2 through the center of the bead. It shows the altitude profile of the bead, allowing to estimate also its extent. The sharp cut off to the left is due to the viewing geometry – the CAM-M view is from the top-right quadrant in this plot – hence, no information are available “behind” the bead.